

THE ANALYSIS OF PROBLEMS IN THE PROCESS OF WORD-FOR-WORD
TRANSLATION OF THE WORK “THE THIRD DOOR” BY ALEX BANAYAN FROM
ENGLISH INTO UZBEK

Iroda Yoqubova Shuhrat qizi

Termiz Davlat Universiteti.

E-mail: irodayoqubova2005@gmail.com

Rahmatullayeva Iroda Valijon qizi

Termiz Davlat Universiteti.

E-mail: irodarahmatullayeva@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11118245>

Abstract. *This article is about the problems encountered in the process of word-for-word translation of “The third door” written by Alex Banayan from English into Uzbek and their analysis. This article provides information about the transformation used.*

Key words: *lexicological analysis, morphological analysis, syntactic analysis, orthographical analysis, punctuational analysis.*

АНАЛИЗ ПРОБЛЕМ В ПРОЦЕССЕ ДОСЛОВНОГО ПЕРЕВОДА “ТРЕТЬЯ ДВЕРЬ”
АЛЕКСА БАНАЯНА С АНГЛИЙСКОГО НА УЗБЕКСКОГО ЯЗЫК.

Аннотация. *Данная статья посвящена проблемам, возникшим в процессе дословного перевода произведения Алекса Банаяна “Третья дверь” с английского на узбекский язык, и их анализу. В статье также представлена информация об используемых преобразованиях.*

Ключевые слова: *лексикологический анализ, морфологический анализ, синтаксический анализ, орфографический анализ, пунктуационный анализ.*

INTRODUCTION

Alex Banayan's „The Third Door” is the best-selling business book by one of the youngest authors in American history. „The Third Door” chronicles Banayan's seven-year quest to uncover a clear mindset for exponential growth and success. This book has been translated into more than ten languages. Literal translation method was used in the translation of the work. The following article highlights the difficulties and problems in the translation process.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Cross-reference, comparative, analytical, statistical methods of research were used in the translation of this article from English to Uzbek.

DISCUSSION

During the translation of this work from English to Uzbek, many transformations had to be made. Including lexicological transformations. Now we will base them on the example of sentences:

„ A treasure chest of wisdom...knowledge that can be used by anyone, anywhere, who wants to take their journey further...Banayan has become one of the most equipped guides to help you climb higher mountains in your life.” [Shawn Achor, „The Happiness Advantage and Big Potential]”

„Donolikning xazina sandig'i...bilimdan sayohatini davom ettirishni xohlagan istalgan odam istalgan joyda foydalana oladi...Banayan sizga hayotingizdagi balandroq tog'larga ko'tarilishingizga yordam beruvchi eng ko'p foydalanilgan qo'llanmaga aylandi.” **Lexicology** is a branch of linguistics that studies the lexicon of a specific language. Learns the root meaning of the word. The word "equipped guides" in the above sentence is translated as "used guide" (foydalanilgan qo'llanma) during the translation process.

This corresponds to a lexicological transformation. That is, the meaning of this word, when translated directly, would be translated as "equipped instructions"(jihozlangan yo'riqnomalar). A little coloring was added to this word, The reason is that the reader should not feel stupid when reading this sentence.

Morphological transformation. *„Unlike any business book I have read. „The Third Door” is an exhilarating thrill ride of hope, joy, ambition, and self-discovery. I cheered out loud, and at different points, tears trickled down my face... „The Third Door” motivated me to turn up the volume in my life... A triumph”. [Maya Watson Banks, Director of marketing at Netflix] „Men o'qigan istalgan biznes kitobdan farqli ravishda, „Uchinchi eshik” umid, shodlik, orzu-istak va o'zini kashf qilishning xursand qiluvchi, zavqli sayohatidir. Men baland qichqirardim va ba'zi paytlarda yuzimdan ko'z yoshlar tomchilab oqardi... „Uchinchi eshik” menga hayotimda shu holatga yetib kelishimga sabab bo'lgan...G'alaba...* **Morphology** - 1) morphological structure of language; 2) the doctrine of word forms. In the first sense, it means an object, and in the second sense, it means the branch of linguistics that studies this object.

If we analyze this sentence according to the method of morphological transformation, the sentence is translated according to all the rules of morphological transformation. That is, the noun in English was also translated into Uzbek as a noun in the process of translation. This sentence is translated in full compliance with the linguistic norms of morphological transformation. That is, the word in the noun group is also translated into this language in the noun group.

Syntactic transformation. Syntax is a part of grammar that studies the methods of combining words into phrases and sentences, and simple sentences into compound sentences, and studies the structure, meaning, interaction and functions of phrases and sentences. „*Once you start reading, you can't stop.*” [Johan Berger, „*Contagious: Why Things Catch on*”] „*Bir marta o'qisangiz o'zingizni to'xtata olmaysiz.*” If we analyze this sentence by the method of syntactic transformation, some words were omitted and some were changed while the sentence was being translated from English to Uzbek.

If this sentence were to be translated into Uzbek, the meaning of the sentence would not come out and the stylistic colorfulness would be damaged. Because this sentence may be correct in English, but in Uzbek this sentence is considered wrong. As an example of omitted sentences, the word "start" is omitted. In fact, this word can be inserted, but more attention was paid to the stylistic color, and this word was omitted to make the sentence more effective. As an example of the word replacement method, we can take the word "yourself". There is no such word in the book.

This word was not added for nothing. The word "you" in the original translation is It was translated as "yourself". That is, the word replacement method was used.

Punctuational transformation. Punctuation is a branch of linguistics that studies the rules of punctuation. „*Unlike any business book I have read. The Third Door is an exhilarating thrill ride of hope, joy, ambition, and self-discovery.*” [Maya Watson Banks, *Director of marketing at Netflix*] „*Men o'qigan istalgan biznes kitobdan farqli ravishda, UCHINCHI ESHIK umid, shodlik, orzu-istak va o'zini kashf qilishning xursand qiluvchi zavqli sayohatidir.*” These sentences were converted into one sentence during the translation process. That is, a comma punctuation mark was used instead of a period separating two sentences.

However, the content of the sentence was not damaged, on the contrary, the sentence became more attractive and colorful. Orthographic transformation. Orthography is a department that studies the rules of correct writing of the literary language. If we analyze this sentence according to the method of orthographic transformation, the sentence is translated according to all the rules of morphological transformation.

CONCLUSION

Each translator, of course, may face different problems when translating a work. The translator must be extremely responsible and take the translation of the work seriously. Because the author of the work may not be able to convey the idea that he wants to convey. Therefore, he should carefully study the subject of the work and what it is about, that is, he should be aware of the history of the work. The translator should have a wide vocabulary, because he should be able

to effectively use synonyms without translating the words found in the work. This helps the work to be read cleanly, without difficulties, does not touch the mind of the reader, and also increases the reader's interest in reading the continuation of the work.

REFERENCES

1. Urinova Tursunoy Urin qizi. (2021) Translation problems of set expressions related businessmen speech Международной научно-практической конференции „Молодой ученый вызовы и перспективы” стр. 120-124
2. Kamoljonovich, S. J., & O'G, Y. N. U. B. (2022). BADIY TARJIMA UCHUN TARJIMA USULLARI TAHLILI (IAN TUHOVSKIY ASARLARI MISOLIDA). *Ta'lim fidoyilari*, 18(5), 32-37.
3. Tarjima nazariyasi: Oliy o'quv yurtlari uchun o'quv qo'llanma/ I.G'ofurov, O.Mo'minov, N.Qambarov. – Toshkent: Tafakkur-Bo'stoni, 2012.216b. e-mail: tafakkur0880@mail.ru
4. Qodirovna, A. Z., & Kamoljonovich, S. J. (2022). JK ROULINGNING, GARRI POTTER VA AFSUNGARLAR TOSHI''ROMANIDAGI SEHRGARLAR OBRAZINI INGLIZ TILIDAN O'ZBEK TILIGA TARJIMA QILISHNING LINGVO-PERSPEKTIV TAHLILI. *Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS)*, 2(3), 176-180. <https://doi.org/10.24412/21812454-2022-3-176-180>